

1. Properties of target stars

HIP ID	OTHER ID	RA ^a	DEC ^a	G	K	Dist.	Age	SpT	M_{SpT}	M_{iso}	m_f
		hms	dms	mag	mag				pc	Myr	
HIP50847	* 191 Car	10 22 58.1465	-66 54 05.385	4.93	5.31	128.9 ± 1.6	27 ± 4	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	4.9 ± 0.5	1
HIP52742	HD 93563	10 46 57.4734	-56 45 25.89	5.12	5.22	178.5 ± 3.6	150 ± 50	B5V	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.1 ^{+0.6} _{-0.4}	1
HIP54767	HD 97583	11 12 45.2069	-64 10 11.171	5.2	5.42	97.7 ± 0.6	100 ⁺⁵⁰ ₋₄₀	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	3.3 ± 0.3	1
HIP58452	HD 104080	11 59 10.6803	-45 49 55.998	6.34	6.53	134.0 ± 0.9	20 ± 5	B8.5V	3.1 ^{+0.6} _{-0.4}	3.0 ± 0.3	0
HIP58901	HD 104900	12 04 45.2597	-59 15 11.703	6.29	6.28	117.0 ± 1.4	13 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.9 ± 0.3	1
HIP59173	V* V863 Cen	12 08 05.2222	-50 39 40.575	4.4	4.87	108.9 ± 2.3	15 ± 3	B5V	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	5.4 ± 0.5	1
HIP59747	* del Cru	12 15 08.7184	-58 44 56.126	2.77	3.53	139.5 ± 13.9	16 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	11.0 ± 1.0	1
HIP60009	* zet Cru	12 18 26.242	-64 00 11.107	4.04	4.53	108.2 ± 2.3	12 ⁺⁴ ₋₂	B2.5V	6.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	6.5 ± 0.6	1
HIP60379	HD 107696	12 22 49.4317	-57 40 34.068	5.36	5.64	104.1 ± 0.8	13 ± 3	B7V	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	3.8 ± 0.4	0
HIP60710	* G Cen	12 26 31.76	-51 27 02.288	4.8	5.23	136.1 ± 3.4	18 ⁺² ₋₃	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	5.6 ± 0.6	1
HIP60823	* sig Cen	12 28 02.3821	-50 13 50.296	3.89	4.48	126.2 ± 3.7	17 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	7.2 ± 0.7	1
HIP60855	* u Cen	12 28 22.4671	-39 02 28.19	5.43	5.54	150.4 ± 3.7	16 ± 3	B8.5V	3.1 ^{+0.6} _{-0.4}	5.0 ± 0.5	1
HIP61257	HD 109195	12 33 12.1871	-52 04 58.236	6.55	6.61	125.8 ± 0.6	17 ± 3	B9.5V	2.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.6}	2.7 ± 0.3	1
HIP61585	* alf Mus	12 37 11.0178	-69 08 08.033	2.7	3.25	116.0 ± 11.2	15 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	9.8 ^{+1.1} _{-1.0}	1
HIP62058	HD 110506	12 43 09.1786	-56 10 34.418	5.98	6.17	123.5 ± 0.6	15 ± 3	B7.5V	3.6 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	3.4 ± 0.3	0
HIP62327	HD 110956	12 46 22.7144	-56 29 19.735	4.61	5.06	117.9 ± 3.1 ^b	17 ± 3	B2.5V	6.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	5.4 ± 0.5	1
HIP62434	* bet Cru	12 47 43.2687	-59 41 19.579	—	1.99	85.4 ± 7.1 ^b	16 ± 3	B1V	11.0 ^{+4.0} _{-1.0}	11.0 ± 1.0	1
HIP62786	HD 111774	12 51 56.931	-39 40 49.55	5.97	6.22	140.3 ± 1.1	17 ± 3	B7.5V	3.6 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	3.7 ± 0.4	0
HIP63003	* mu.01 Cru	12 54 35.6242	-57 10 40.528	4.0	4.58	124.8 ± 3.3	16 ± 3	B2V-V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	7.1 ± 0.7	1
HIP63005	* mu.02 Cru	12 54 36.8841	-57 10 07.193	5.15	5.31	121.0 ± 1.7	16 ± 3	B5V	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.7 ± 0.5	1
HIP63210	* H Cen	12 57 04.3514	-51 11 55.512	5.14	5.34	128.8 ± 1.7	19 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	4.8 ± 0.5	1
HIP63945	* f Cen	13 06 16.7036	-48 27 47.846	4.67	5.05	122.6 ± 2.3	15 ± 3	B4V	5.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	5.5 ± 0.5	1
HIP64004	* ksi02 Cen	13 06 54.6394	-49 54 22.487	4.22	4.84	147.1 ± 3.9	20 ± 4	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	7.0 ± 0.7	1
HIP65021	HD 115583	13 19 43.4213	-67 21 51.567	7.25	7.22	171.4 ± 0.7	16 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.9 ± 0.3	0
HIP65112	V* V964 Cen	13 20 37.8253	-52 44 52.169	5.43	5.8	119.2 ± 1.4	15 ± 3	B5V	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.0 ± 0.4	0
HIP66454	HD 118354	13 37 23.476	-46 25 40.432	5.89	6.14	143.0 ± 2.7	17 ± 3	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	4.0 ± 0.4	1
HIP67464	* nu. Cen	13 49 30.2765	-41 41 15.75	3.38	4.24	124.3 ± 5.4	18 ⁺³ ₋₅	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	8.2 ± 0.8	1
HIP67669	* 3 Cen A	13 51 49.6013	-32 59 38.706	4.51	4.97	105.4 ± 9.9 ^b	17 ± 3	B5V+B9V	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.8 ± 0.5	1
HIP67703	* N Cen	13 52 04.8623	-52 48 41.506	5.25	5.51	93.1 ± 0.8	16 ± 3	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	3.4 ± 0.3	1
HIP68245	* phi Cen	13 58 16.2661	-42 06 02.724	3.81	4.49	140.8 ± 5.4	17 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	7.9 ± 0.8	0
HIP68282	* ups01 Cen	13 58 40.7486	-44 48 12.908	3.85	4.47	131.1 ± 2.7 ^b	21 ⁺⁴ ₋₂	B2V-V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	6.6 ± 0.7	1
HIP68862	* chi Cen	14 06 02.768	-41 10 46.678	4.31	4.93	154.1 ± 5.1	25 ± 5	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	6.8 ± 0.7	0
HIP69011	HD 123247	14 07 40.808	-48 42 14.498	6.42	6.43	97.6 ± 0.5	17 ± 3	B9.5V	2.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.6}	2.3 ± 0.2	0
HIP69618	V* V795 Cen	14 14 57.1383	-57 05 10.049	5.01	4.77	131.5 ± 2.3	2 ± 1	B4V	5.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	6.3 ^{+0.6} _{-3.0}	0
HIP70300	* a Cen	14 23 02.2387	-39 30 42.544	4.36	4.92	120.1 ± 2.6	17 ⁺³ ₋₅	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	5.9 ± 0.6	2
HIP70626	HD 126475	14 26 49.8732	-39 52 26.344	6.34	6.59	141.0 ± 1.1	15 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	3.3 ± 0.3	0
HIP71352	* eta Cen	14 35 30.4241	-42 09 28.17	2.25	2.96	93.7 ± 1.8 ^b	15 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	9.7 ± 1.0	3
HIP71353	HD 127971	14 35 31.479	-41 31 02.792	5.86	6.03	108.3 ± 2.6	15 ± 3	B7V	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	3.2 ± 0.3	1
HIP71453	HD 128207	14 36 44.1322	-40 12 41.696	5.72	6.01	136.4 ± 1.5	16 ± 3	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	4.0 ± 0.4	0
HIP71536	* rho Lup	14 37 53.2261	-49 25 32.981	4.0	4.51	107.0 ± 2.3	14 ± 4	B3/4V	5.2 ^{+0.8} _{-0.3}	6.2 ± 0.6	1
HIP71860	* alf Lup	14 41 55.7557	-47 23 17.515	2.32	2.67	142.5 ± 3.4 ^b	19 ± 3	B1.5V	10.0 ^{+1.0} _{-3.0}	11.0 ± 1.0	1
HIP71865	* b Cen	14 41 57.5905	-37 47 36.58	3.99	4.49	99.7 ± 3.1	15 ± 2	B2.5V	6.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	5.9 ± 0.6	1
HIP73266	HD 132094	14 58 24.2646	-37 21 44.902	7.26	7.28	170.9 ± 1.2	15 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.7 ± 0.3	1

HIP73624	HD 132955	15 02 59.2764	-32 38 35.849	5.42	5.73	146.7 ± 2.8	17 ± 3	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	5.0 ± 0.5	1
HIP74100	HD 133937	15 08 39.198	-42 52 04.522	5.81	6.1	144.2 ± 1.6	19 ± 3	B5/7V	4.3 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.1 ± 0.4	1
HIP74449	* e Lup	15 12 49.5875	-44 30 01.49	4.79	5.28	138.2 ± 3.9	18 ± 3	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	5.7 ± 0.6	1
HIP74657	HD 135174	15 15 19.6424	-44 08 58.18	6.73	6.95	154.9 ± 1.2	18 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	3.0 ± 0.3	0
HIP74752	HD 135454	15 16 37.1496	-42 22 12.565	6.75	6.83	130.9 ± 0.7	14 ± 3	B9.5V	2.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.6}	2.6 ± 0.3	1
HIP74950	V* GG Lup	15 18 56.3746	-40 47 17.596	5.57	6.21	150.1 ± 2.0	18 ± 3	B7V	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	4.4 ± 0.4	1
HIP75141	* del Lup	15 21 22.3138	-40 38 51.109	3.21	3.96	148.6 ± 10.6	16 ± 4	B1.5V	10.0 ^{+1.0} _{-3.0}	9.8 ^{+1.1} _{-1.0}	1
HIP75304	* phi02 Lup	15 23 09.3506	-36 51 30.557	4.51	4.94	159.2 ± 5.1 ^b	15 ± 3	B4V	5.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	7.1 ± 0.7	1
HIP75647	HD 137432	15 27 18.1304	-36 46 03.214	5.43	5.84	142.3 ± 2.4	17 ± 3	B5V	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.6 ± 0.5	1
HIP76048	HD 138221	15 31 50.2295	-32 52 52.015	6.45	6.25	163.7 ± 1.0	2 ± 1	B7V	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	3.3 ^{+1.6} _{-0.3}	0
HIP76126	* zet Lib	15 32 55.2212	-16 51 10.241	5.48	5.89	230.8 ± 8.4	11 ± 3	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	7.2 ± 0.7	1
HIP76591	HD 139233	15 38 32.6385	-39 09 38.52	6.58	6.76	145.7 ± 1.0	17 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	3.0 ± 0.3	0
HIP76600	* tau Lib	15 38 39.3694	-29 46 39.895	3.65	4.12	112.5 ± 2.5 ^b	13 ⁺⁴ ₋₃	B2.5V	6.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	7.5 ± 0.7	1
HIP76633	HD 139486	15 39 00.0577	-19 43 57.199	7.63	7.49	164.7 ± 1.0	7 ⁺³ ₋₂	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.4 ± 0.2	0
HIP77562	HD 141168	15 50 07.0836	-53 12 35.174	5.77	5.95	96.5 ± 0.5	17 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.9 ± 0.3	0
HIP77968	HD 142256	15 55 22.8856	-44 31 33.651	6.96	6.99	181.9 ± 1.0	17 ⁺⁵ ₋₂	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	3.4 ± 0.3	0
HIP78104	* rho Sco	15 56 53.0772	-29 12 50.667	3.87	4.46	136.6 ± 5.5	14 ⁺² ₋₃	B2V-V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	7.9 ± 0.8	1
HIP78168	HD 142883	15 57 40.4636	-20 58 59.082	5.81	5.73	157.4 ± 1.3	10 ± 3	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	5.3 ± 0.5	1
HIP78207	* 48 Lib	15 58 11.3682	-14 16 45.681	4.74	4.59	139.8 ± 2.4	0.5 ^{+0.5} _{-0.3}	B5Vp	4.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	4.7 ± 0.5	0
HIP78324	HD 143022	15 59 30.8817	-40 51 54.598	8.12	7.49	167.2 ± 1.0	7 ± 2	B9.5V	2.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.6}	2.1 ± 0.2	0
HIP78384	* eta Lup	16 00 07.3279	-38 23 48.138	3.41	4.1	135.5 ± 3.3 ^b	14 ± 3	B2.5V	6.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	9.1 ± 0.9	1
HIP78655	HD 143699	16 03 24.1895	-38 36 09.141	4.87	5.27	122.5 ± 4.5 ^b	14 ± 3	B5/7V	4.3 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	5.1 ± 0.5	0
HIP78702	HD 143956	16 04 00.2383	-19 46 02.926	7.76	7.24	148.4 ± 0.8	10 ⁺² ₋₅	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.4 ± 0.2	1
HIP78918	* tet Lup	16 06 35.5439	-36 48 08.173	4.16	4.7	135.7 ± 4.7	17 ± 3	B2.5V	6.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	6.9 ± 0.7	1
HIP78933	* ome Sco	16 06 48.4249	-20 40 09.079	3.92	4.01	140.9 ± 5.4	11 ± 3	B1V	11.0 ^{+4.0} _{-1.0}	9.8 ± 1.0	0
HIP78968	HD 144586	16 07 14.9283	-17 56 09.731	7.76	7.4	149.1 ± 0.6	9 ⁺³ ₋₂	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.4 ± 0.2	0
HIP79044	HD 144591	16 08 04.3798	-36 13 54.598	6.74	6.91	138.5 ± 0.9	17 ± 3	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.7 ± 0.3	1
HIP79404	* 13 Sco	16 12 18.2046	-27 55 34.953	4.53	4.98	147.4 ± 3.1	11 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	7.4 ± 0.7	1
HIP80142	HD 147001	16 21 27.0327	-48 11 19.041	6.5	6.62	176.3 ± 1.2	17 ± 3	B7V	3.9 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	3.9 ± 0.4	1
HIP80208	HD 147152	16 22 27.9955	-49 34 20.468	5.07	5.4	141.8 ± 6.4 ^b	17 ± 3	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	5.4 ± 0.5	0
HIP80569	* chi Oph	16 27 01.4355	-18 27 22.499	4.2	3.02	152.9 ± 4.6	7 ⁺³ ₋₄	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	11.0 ± 1.0	1
HIP80911	* N Sco	16 31 22.9344	-34 42 15.725	4.18	4.69	182.4 ± 6.8	16 ± 4	B2V-V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	8.8 ± 0.9	0
HIP81208	HD 149274	16 35 13.8392	-35 43 28.725	6.63	6.77	146.1 ± 1.0	17 ⁺³ ₋₄	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	2.6 ± 0.3	1
HIP81266	* tau Sco	16 35 52.9528	-28 12 57.661	2.8	3.57	195.2 ± 42.3	12 ⁺² ₋₄	B0.2V	17.7 ^{+0.8} _{-2.7}	12.0 ^{+2.0} _{-1.0}	1
HIP81316	HD 149425	16 36 28.673	-40 18 10.916	7.07	6.71	184.4 ± 1.0	18 ± 4	B9V	2.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	3.9 ± 0.4	1
HIP81472	V* V1003 Sco	16 38 26.2919	-43 23 54.328	5.81	5.93	190.9 ± 1.9	17 ± 3	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	5.7 ± 0.6	1
HIP81474	HD 149914	16 38 28.6527	-18 13 13.713	6.64	5.69	154.4 ± 0.6	2.0 ^{+0.5} _{-0.2}	B9.5V	2.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.6}	3.1 ^{+1.6} _{-0.3}	1
HIP81891	HD 150638	16 43 38.7239	-32 06 21.406	6.45	6.63	153.0 ± 1.0	14 ± 3	B8V	3.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	3.4 ± 0.3	0
HIP81914	HD 150591	16 43 54.082	-41 06 48.038	6.12	6.29	174.6 ± 1.6	17 ± 3	B6/7V	4.1 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	4.7 ± 0.5	1
HIP81972	HD 150742	16 44 42.5926	-40 50 22.83	5.61	5.84	173.8 ± 1.9	18 ± 3	B3V	5.4 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}	5.6 ± 0.6	1
HIP82514	* mu.01 Sco	16 51 52.2283	-38 02 50.638	3.07	3.7	169.5 ± 8.6 ^c	20 ± 4	B1V+BV	11.0 ^{+4.0} _{-1.0}	10.0 ± 1.0	1
HIP82545	* mu.02 Sco	16 52 20.1453	-38 01 03.125	3.54	4.29	169.5 ± 8.6 ^c	20 ± 4	B2V	7.0 ^{+3.0} _{-1.0}	9.1 ± 0.3	0

Table 1. Revised stellar parameters for all the targets of the BEAST survey. The multiplicity flag m_f indicates whether the star is known to be a multiple system (1: ?, 2: this work, 3: ?) or not (0).

Notes. ^a: coordinates are given in J2000 IRCS. ^b: using Hipparcos parallax. ^c: see ?.

2. Observation table

HIP ID	OTHER ID	DATE OBS	FILTER	DIT(s)×NDIT×NEXP	Δ PA ($^\circ$) ^a	Seeing ($''$) ^b	Airmass ^b	τ_0 (ms) ^{a,b}	Program ID
HIP 67669	* 3 Cen A	2019-02-22	DB_K12	32x6x46	72.5	0.5	1.01	12.4	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 67669	* 3 Cen A	2019-02-22	OBS_H	64x1x46	71.9	0.5	1.01	12.4	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 50847	* L Car	2019-01-26	DB_K12	64x3x46	15.2	0.41	1.49	17.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 52742	HD 93563	2018-05-14	DB_K12	64x3x46	22.0	0.78	1.18	3.1	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 52742	HD 93563	2018-05-14	OBS_H	64x1x46	22.1	0.79	1.18	3.1	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 52742	HD 93563	2019-01-26	DB_K12	64x3x46	22.1	0.51	1.18	10.7	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 52742	HD 93563	2019-01-26	OBS_H	64x1x46	22.2	0.51	1.18	10.8	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 52742	HD 93563	2020-03-20	DB_K12	64x3x46	22.3	0.95	1.18	5.0	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 52742	HD 93563	2020-03-20	OBS_H	64x1x46	22.4	0.96	1.18	5.1	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 54767	HD 97583	2019-02-24	DB_K12	32x6x42	11.7	0.55	1.3	19.5	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 54767	HD 97583	2019-02-24	OBS_H	64x1x42	16.0	0.56	1.3	18.4	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 54767	HD 97583	2019-03-12	DB_K12	64x3x46	18.5	0.59	1.3	8.3	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 54767	HD 97583	2019-03-12	OBS_H	64x1x46	18.6	0.59	1.3	8.3	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 54767	HD 97583	2020-02-21	DB_K12	64x3x46	18.7	0.64	1.3	6.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 54767	HD 97583	2020-02-21	OBS_H	64x1x46	18.7	0.65	1.3	6.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 58452	HD 104080	2018-04-09	DB_K12	32x6x46	31.9	0.5	1.08	9.5	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 58452	HD 104080	2018-04-09	OBS_H	32x1x46	32.5	0.49	1.08	9.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 58452	HD 104080	2020-02-01	DB_K12	64x3x46	32.4	0.52	1.07	4.4	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 58452	HD 104080	2020-02-01	OBS_H	64x1x46	32.4	0.52	1.07	4.3	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 58901	HD 104900	2019-02-20	DB_K12	64x3x46	20.7	1.11	1.22	3.8	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 58901	HD 104900	2019-02-20	OBS_H	64x1x46	20.8	1.11	1.22	3.9	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 58901	HD 104900	2021-03-17	DB_K12	64x3x46	20.8	0.54	1.22	5.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 58901	HD 104900	2021-03-17	OBS_H	64x1x46	20.9	0.54	1.22	5.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 59173	HD 105382	2019-03-12	DB_K12	32x6x46	26.9	0.58	1.12	6.9	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 59173	HD 105382	2019-03-12	OBS_H	64x1x46	26.6	0.58	1.12	6.8	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 59173	HD 105382	2020-02-21	DB_K12	32x6x46	27.2	0.73	1.12	5.2	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 59173	HD 105382	2020-02-21	OBS_H	64x1x46	26.7	0.72	1.12	5.3	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 59173	HD 105382	2020-03-02	DB_K12	32x6x46	27.2	0.55	1.12	10.8	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 59173	HD 105382	2020-03-02	OBS_H	64x1x46	26.8	0.55	1.12	10.7	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 60009	* zet Cru	2019-02-23	DB_K12	32x6x46	19.0	0.57	1.3	11.5	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 60009	* zet Cru	2019-02-23	OBS_H	32x1x46	19.3	0.58	1.3	11.2	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 60009	* zet Cru	2020-02-08	DB_K12	32x6x46	19.1	0.52	1.3	7.8	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 60009	* zet Cru	2020-02-08	OBS_H	32x1x46	19.3	0.52	1.3	7.8	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 60379	HD 107696	2019-02-24	DB_K12	32x6x44	22.0	0.43	1.2	16.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 60379	HD 107696	2019-02-24	OBS_H	64x1x44	21.7	0.43	1.2	16.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 60379	HD 107696	2021-03-19	DB_K12	64x3x46	21.5	0.44	1.2	5.0	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 60379	HD 107696	2021-03-19	OBS_H	64x1x46	21.5	0.44	1.2	5.0	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 60823	* sig Cen	2019-02-25	DB_K12	32x6x46	27.6	0.91	1.11	4.7	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 60823	* sig Cen	2019-02-25	OBS_H	32x1x46	28.1	0.94	1.11	4.5	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 60823	* sig Cen	2021-03-07	DB_K12	32x6x46	27.6	0.44	1.11	16.9	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 60823	* sig Cen	2021-03-07	OBS_H	32x1x46	28.0	0.44	1.11	16.7	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 61585	* alf Mus	2019-03-15	DB_K12	8x23x45	18.0	0.59	1.4	5.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 61585	* alf Mus	2019-03-15	OBS_H	8x1x45	18.5	0.57	1.4	5.2	1101.C-0258(B)

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Table 2 – continued from previous page

HIP ID	OTHER ID	DATE OBS	FILTER	DIT(s)×NDIT×NEXP	Δ PA ($^{\circ}$) ^a	Seeing ($''$) ^b	Airmass ^b	τ_0 (ms) ^{a,b}	Program ID
HIP 61585	* alf Mus	2021-04-06	DB_K12	8x23x45	18.0	0.57	1.41	12.2	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 61585	* alf Mus	2021-04-06	OBS_H	8x1x45	18.4	0.57	1.41	12.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 62058	HD 110506	2019-03-16	DB_K12	64x3x46	22.2	0.85	1.18	4.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 62058	HD 110506	2019-03-16	OBS_H	64x1x46	20.8	0.85	1.18	4.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 62058	HD 110506	2021-04-06	DB_K12	64x3x46	18.8	0.87	1.24	6.9	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 62058	HD 110506	2021-04-06	OBS_H	64x1x46	18.9	0.87	1.24	7.0	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 62327	HD 110956	2019-03-29	DB_K12	32x6x46	22.7	0.72	1.18	7.2	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 62327	HD 110956	2019-03-29	OBS_H	64x1x46	22.5	0.73	1.18	7.2	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 62327	HD 110956	2020-03-17	DB_K12	32x6x46	22.8	0.76	1.18	4.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 62327	HD 110956	2020-03-17	OBS_H	64x1x46	22.4	0.76	1.18	4.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 62434	* bet Cru	2019-04-01	DB_K12	2x72x42	22.6	0.87	1.22	3.2	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 62434	* bet Cru	2022-04-05	DB_K12	2x72x42	22.6	0.49	1.23	6.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 63003	* mu.01 Cru	2018-06-04	DB_K12	32x6x46	18.1	0.44	1.19	3.5	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 63003	* mu.01 Cru	2018-06-04	OBS_H	32x1x46	17.0	0.45	1.19	3.5	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 63003	* mu.01 Cru	2019-04-09	DB_K12	16x12x46	22.9	0.55	1.19	9.0	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 63003	* mu.01 Cru	2019-04-09	OBS_H	16x1x46	23.9	0.56	1.19	8.8	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 63005	* mu.02 Cru	2019-03-05	DB_K12	64x3x46	21.8	0.51	1.19	5.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 63005	* mu.02 Cru	2019-03-05	OBS_H	64x1x46	21.9	0.51	1.19	5.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 63005	* mu.02 Cru	2022-02-27	DB_K12	64x3x46	22.0	0.37	1.19	12.0	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 63005	* mu.02 Cru	2022-02-27	OBS_H	64x1x46	22.0	0.37	1.19	12.1	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 63945	* f Cen	2018-04-23	DB_K12	32x6x46	29.3	0.69	1.1	7.3	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 63945	* f Cen	2018-04-23	OBS_H	32x1x46	29.8	0.69	1.1	7.5	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 63945	* f Cen	2019-04-10	DB_K12	32x3x42	14.9	0.56	1.1	13.2	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 63945	* f Cen	2019-04-10	OBS_H	32x1x42	20.0	0.59	1.1	12.9	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 65021	HD 115583	2018-05-17	DB_K12	64x3x46	17.3	0.3	1.37	15.6	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 65021	HD 115583	2018-05-17	OBS_H	64x1x46	17.4	0.3	1.37	15.6	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 65021	HD 115583	2020-02-21	DB_K12	64x3x46	17.5	0.96	1.37	4.4	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 65021	HD 115583	2020-02-21	OBS_H	64x1x46	17.6	0.96	1.37	4.5	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 65112	V* V964 Cen	2019-03-21	DB_K12	64x3x46	24.8	0.43	1.14	7.4	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 65112	V* V964 Cen	2019-03-21	OBS_H	64x1x46	25.0	0.43	1.14	7.4	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 65112	V* V964 Cen	2020-03-02	DB_K12	64x3x46	25.1	0.61	1.14	7.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 65112	V* V964 Cen	2020-03-02	OBS_H	64x1x46	25.1	0.61	1.14	7.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 65112	V* V964 Cen	2021-04-16	DB_H23	64x3x46	25.0	0.55	1.14	5.2	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 65112	V* V964 Cen	2021-04-16	OBS_YJ	64x1x46	24.8	0.55	1.14	5.1	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 66454	HD 118354	2018-05-16	DB_K12	64x3x46	30.7	0.52	1.08	5.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 66454	HD 118354	2018-05-16	OBS_H	64x1x46	30.8	0.52	1.08	5.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 66454	HD 118354	2020-02-24	DB_K12	64x3x46	31.6	0.4	1.08	12.4	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 66454	HD 118354	2020-02-24	OBS_H	64x1x46	31.3	0.4	1.08	12.1	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 67464	* nu. Cen	2018-05-05	DB_K12	2x96x42	10.7	0.28	1.05	11.7	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 67464	* nu. Cen	2018-05-05	OBS_H	16x1x42	32.4	0.26	1.05	11.6	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 67464	* nu. Cen	2019-02-23	DB_K12	16x12x46	41.0	0.38	1.05	10.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 67464	* nu. Cen	2019-02-23	OBS_H	16x1x46	42.9	0.37	1.05	10.2	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2019-02-24	DB_K12	32x6x42	15.8	0.66	1.14	12.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2019-02-24	OBS_H	64x1x42	17.1	0.67	1.14	11.7	1101.C-0258(B)

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Table 2 – continued from previous page

HIP ID	OTHER ID	DATE OBS	FILTER	DIT(s)×NDIT×NEXP	Δ PA (°) ^a	Seeing (") ^b	Airmass ^b	τ_0 (ms) ^{a,b}	Program ID
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2019-02-25	DB_K12	64x3x46	24.7	1.37	1.14	3.5	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2019-02-25	OBS_H	64x1x46	24.8	1.37	1.14	3.5	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2019-03-24	DB_K12	64x3x46	24.9	0.61	1.14	8.6	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2019-03-24	OBS_H	64x1x46	24.95	0.61	1.14	8.6	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2020-03-20	DB_K12	64x3x46	25.0	0.87	1.14	4.6	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 67703	* N Cen	2020-03-20	OBS_H	64x1x46	26.39	1.15	1.14	3.8	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 68245	* phi Cen	2018-05-28	DB_K12	32x6x46	39.1	0.68	1.05	3.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 68245	* phi Cen	2018-05-28	OBS_H	32x1x46	39.7	0.68	1.05	3.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 68282	* ups01 Cen	2019-03-27	DB_K12	16x12x42	34.9	0.52	1.07	6.2	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 68282	* ups01 Cen	2019-03-27	OBS_H	16x1x42	36.4	0.52	1.07	6.4	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 68282	* ups01 Cen	2021-03-07	DB_K12	32x6x46	34.3	0.35	1.07	15.3	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 68282	* ups01 Cen	2021-03-07	OBS_H	32x1x46	34.8	0.35	1.07	15.6	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 69011	HD 123247	2019-05-31	DB_K12	64x3x46	28.8	0.81	1.1	2.7	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 69011	HD 123247	2019-05-31	OBS_H	64x1x46	28.9	0.81	1.1	2.7	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 70300	* a Cen	2019-03-16	DB_K12	32x6x46	44.9	1.12	1.04	3.2	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 70300	* a Cen	2019-03-16	OBS_H	64x1x46	44.5	1.12	1.04	3.2	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 70300	* a Cen	2019-04-09	DB_K12	32x6x46	44.9	0.6	1.04	5.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 70300	* a Cen	2019-04-09	OBS_H	64x1x46	44.5	0.61	1.04	5.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 70626	HD 126475	2018-04-23	DB_K12	64x3x46	43.4	0.53	1.04	9.2	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 70626	HD 126475	2018-04-23	OBS_H	64x1x46	43.4	0.53	1.04	9.1	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 71352	* eta Cen	2019-03-12	DB_K12	4x42x44	37.5	0.72	1.06	8.0	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 71352	* eta Cen	2019-03-12	OBS_H	4x1x44	38.1	0.71	1.06	7.9	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 71352	* eta Cen	2020-03-02	DB_K12	4x42x44	41.2	0.63	1.05	6.8	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71352	* eta Cen	2020-03-02	OBS_H	4x1x44	42.1	0.63	1.05	6.9	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2019-03-15	DB_K12	32x6x46	28.2	0.89	1.11	3.3	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2019-03-15	OBS_H	32x1x46	28.7	0.92	1.11	3.3	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2020-03-11	OBS_H	32x1x42	33.8	0.76	1.1	5.6	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2021-04-16	DB_K12	32x6x46	28.1	0.82	1.11	4.2	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2021-04-16	OBS_H	32x1x46	28.5	0.83	1.11	4.2	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2021-07-17	DB_K12	32x6x46	28.3	0.61	1.11	4.1	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71536	* rho Lup	2021-07-17	OBS_H	32x1x46	28.7	0.62	1.11	3.9	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 71865	* b Cen	2019-03-21	DB_K12	16x12x42	51.5	0.44	1.03	7.3	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 71865	* b Cen	2019-03-21	OBS_H	16x1x42	53.8	0.44	1.03	7.6	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 71865	* b Cen	2021-04-11	DB_J23	16x12x23	49.1	0.7	1.03	4.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 74100	HD 133937	2019-03-24	DB_K12	64x3x46	36.6	0.52	1.06	9.4	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 74100	HD 133937	2019-03-24	OBS_H	64x1x46	36.7	0.54	1.06	9.3	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 74100	HD 133937	2020-03-07	DB_K12	64x3x46	37.0	1.02	1.06	4.7	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 74100	HD 133937	2020-03-07	OBS_H	64x1x46	37.0	1.02	1.06	4.7	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 74950	V* GG Lup	2019-03-27	DB_K12	64x3x46	25.9	0.71	1.04	3.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 74950	V* GG Lup	2019-03-27	OBS_H	64x1x46	25.9	0.71	1.04	3.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 74950	V* GG Lup	2019-04-29	DB_K12	64x3x46	41.4	0.45	1.04	9.8	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 74950	V* GG Lup	2019-04-29	OBS_H	64x1x46	41.4	0.45	1.04	9.8	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 74950	V* GG Lup	2020-03-23	DB_K12	64x3x46	41.4	0.61	1.04	9.4	1101.C-0258(D)

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Table 2 – continued from previous page

HIP ID	OTHER ID	DATE OBS	FILTER	DIT(s)×NDIT×NEXP	Δ PA (°) ^a	Seeing (") ^b	Airmass ^b	τ_0 (ms) ^{a,b}	Program ID
HIP 74950	V* GG Lup	2020-03-23	OBS_H	64x1x46	41.5	0.61	1.04	9.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 76591	HD 139233	2018-04-23	DB_K12	64x3x46	45.2	0.63	1.03	9.3	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 76591	HD 139233	2018-04-23	OBS_H	64x1x46	45.3	0.64	1.03	9.2	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 76591	HD 139233	2021-07-21	DB_K12	64x3x46	45.3	0.42	1.04	7.8	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 76591	HD 139233	2021-07-21	OBS_H	64x1x46	45.4	0.42	1.04	7.8	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 76600	* tau Lib	2019-04-09	OBS_H	16x1x46	3.6	0.47	1.01	7.7	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 76600	* tau Lib	2019-07-27	DB_K12	16x12x46	90.9	0.54	1.01	4.6	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 76633	HD 139486	2018-05-16	DB_K12	64x3x46	100.2	0.69	1.01	7.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 76633	HD 139486	2018-05-16	OBS_H	64x1x46	100.4	0.69	1.01	8.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 77562	HD 141168	2019-03-21	DB_K12	64x3x46	24.5	0.88	1.14	5.3	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 77562	HD 141168	2019-03-21	OBS_H	64x1x46	24.6	0.88	1.14	5.1	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 77562	HD 141168	2021-05-17	DB_K12	64x3x46	24.8	0.43	1.14	7.5	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 77562	HD 141168	2021-05-17	OBS_H	64x1x46	24.8	0.43	1.14	7.4	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 77968	HD 142256	2018-06-23	DB_K12	64x3x46	34.1	0.62	1.07	5.3	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 77968	HD 142256	2018-06-23	OBS_H	64x1x46	34.2	0.62	1.07	5.3	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 77968	HD 142256	2021-06-27	DB_K12	64x3x46	34.3	0.64	1.07	4.2	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 77968	HD 142256	2021-06-27	OBS_H	64x1x46	34.4	0.64	1.07	4.2	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 78207	* 48 Lib	2018-04-09	DB_K12	16x12x46	46.3	0.48	1.03	7.8	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 78207	* 48 Lib	2018-04-09	OBS_H	32x1x46	46.2	0.48	1.03	7.9	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 79044	HD 144591	2019-03-22	DB_K12	64x3x46	53.9	0.81	1.02	5.7	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 79044	HD 144591	2019-03-22	OBS_H	64x1x46	53.9	0.81	1.02	5.7	1101.C-0258(B)
HIP 79044	HD 144591	2021-04-11	DB_K12	64x3x46	55.0	0.64	1.02	4.7	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 79044	HD 144591	2021-04-11	OBS_H	64x1x46	55.2	0.64	1.02	4.7	1101.C-0258(D)
HIP 80911	* N Sco	2018-08-13	DB_K12	32x6x46	63.0	0.78	1.02	4.7	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 80911	* N Sco	2018-08-13	OBS_H	32x1x46	63.9	0.77	1.02	4.7	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 80911	* N Sco	2019-07-06	DB_K12	32x6x46	63.1	0.6	1.02	5.1	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 80911	* N Sco	2019-07-06	OBS_H	32x1x46	63.9	0.59	1.02	5.1	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 82514	* mu.01 Sco	2018-05-15	DB_K12	8x24x46	48.8	0.7	1.03	3.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 82514	* mu.01 Sco	2018-05-15	OBS_H	8x1x46	52.1	0.69	1.04	3.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 82514	* mu.01 Sco	2019-08-04	DB_K12	8x24x46	53.4	0.52	1.03	3.7	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 82514	* mu.01 Sco	2019-08-04	OBS_H	8x1x46	57.3	0.54	1.03	3.4	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 82545	* mu.02 Sco	2018-04-24	DB_K12	16x12x46	51.1	0.64	1.03	4.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 82545	* mu.02 Sco	2018-04-24	OBS_H	16x1x46	53.3	0.63	1.03	4.0	1101.C-0258(A)
HIP 82545	* mu.02 Sco	2021-06-04	DB_K12	16x12x46	51.3	0.47	1.03	10.4	1101.C-0258(C)
HIP 82545	* mu.02 Sco	2021-06-04	OBS_H	16x1x46	53.2	0.48	1.03	10.1	1101.C-0258(C)

Table 2. Observing logs for all stars within the sample

Notes. ^a: DIT correspond to the Detector Integration Time per frame. Δ PA is the amplitude of the parallactic rotation. τ_0 correspond to the coherence time. ^b: values extracted from the updated DIMM info, averaged over the sequence.

3. Mean probability detection maps using various ages and models

Figure 1 shows the mean probability detection maps for the minimum, average and maximum age estimates of the sample's stars and the 3 distinct evolutionary models (atmo2020 (?), ames-cond (?), ames-dusty (?)) that we used to convert detection limits in contrast into detection limits in masses.

4. Individual probability detection maps

Figures 2–7 show the individual probability detection maps for each star in the studied sample.

Fig. 1. Mean probability detection maps computed using 3 different model and the nominal, minimum and maximum age for all stars indicated in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Probability detection maps for every observations within our sample, computed using the cond model and the nominal age.

Fig. 3. Probability detection maps for every observations within our sample, computed using the cond model and the nominal age.

Fig. 4. Probability detection maps for every observations within our sample, computed using the cond model and the nominal age.

Fig. 5. Probability detection maps for every observations within our sample, computed using the cond model and the nominal age.

Fig. 6. Probability detection maps for every observations within our sample, computed using the cond model and the nominal age.

Fig. 7. Probability detection maps for every observations within our sample, computed using the cond model and the nominal age.